

ASSESSMENT OF TEACHING QUALITY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN ILORIN METROPOLIS, KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract : *This study assessed teaching quality among secondary schools teachers' in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. A descriptive survey research type was employed for this study. Thirty public secondary schools were sampled through stratified random sampling techniques. Furthermore, 108 respondents were selected randomly which were used as sample for this research. This comprised of 36 principals and 72 vice-principals. Three research questions guided this study. A questionnaire titled "Teaching Quality Assessment Questionnaire" was employed for the collection of data. Mean score and standard deviation were utilised analysing the data obtained. The study showed that, teaching quality by teachers within secondary school in Ilorin metropolis was at average level with mean value 2.98; the most important factors militating against the teaching quality among secondary school teachers were lack of creativity and innovativeness to improvise for unavailable instructional materials, lack of vibrant staff development programmes, low staff morale and ineffective teaching methods used by teachers with mean values 3.95, 3.91, 3.64 and 3.53 correspondingly. Based on the results, the study suggested that the government should expose teachers to regular staff development programmes in teaching methodology in areas such as instructional strategies and effective classroom management in order to enhance their teaching quality. This can be done by organizing conferences, workshops and seminars to facilitate in keeping up-to-date of the problems postulated by contemporary day classroom.*

Introduction

Education is a life-long practice that originates naturally and ongoing till demise. Many education specialists have seen the meaning of education from various viewpoints. Generally, it is obvious In all that education is an essential to the attainment of human and national society. Oyedeki (2012) drive this point further by stating that education as a process allows people to control themselves to the societal situation. It is not only for developing skilled human resources for industries and the civil service but it is also a means of raising the political and social awareness of the citizens. This explains why generally in education and particularly in secondary education is a germane to the growth and development of any nation.

Secondary instruction is therefore, the system of education where learners acquire after

basic education and before the tertiary level. Its pertinent centred on the situations both as the connection between primary and tertiary education and the instrument in formulating individuals for suitable existence in the society (Duze, 2012). In specific terms, Nigerian secondary education is expected to:

- a) make an aggregate numbers of learners in primary school with the prospect for education of a higher quality, irrespective of religious, social, sex and ethnic upbringing;
- b) prepare learners to effectively live in our contemporary age of science and technology;
- c) promote a group of people who can reflect for themselves, respect the opinions and feeling of others, respect the self-esteem of

labour, and appraise those principles stated under the extensive national goals and live as good citizens;

- d) stimulate learners with an aspiration for self-improvement and achievement both at college and in later life (National Policy on Education, 2004, p.16)

All the identified aims are thoroughly linked with quality education since John Dewey precisely pointed out that, every capability of man enumerated as learning. This implies that quality teaching is the utmost vital in achieving of secondary education aims and objectives. It is relatively disastrous that secondary schools currently are not gauging the typical anticipated of the policy because of the inadequate rate at which senior secondary students are producing in their terminal Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations. Attesting to this, Akinola (2010) maintained that secondary schools students' academic performance in external examinations conducted by the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO), have been abysmally poor, and this is to the disappointment of the general public.

However, as a result of the nefarious of this difficulty in Nigeria, especially Kwara State, the shareholders in education are inquisitive to query more about the source or relative causes for this challenge. According to Jimoh (2013), factors that influence students' academic performance are unending which include family size, economic status of the family and environment factor. Other factors as noted by Anyanwu, Anyanwu & Ansa (2014), Adodo & Gbore (2012) and Asikhia (2010) are teacher' related factors like teachers characteristics (teacher qualification, experience and teaching effectiveness). Onuekwe (2015) stressed further that there are eight key sources of poor academic achievement among which quality delivery of instruction (teaching quality) tops other factors.

Teaching according to the National Open University of Nigeria (2015), is a manner in which specific situations are set for the students deliberately to improve their understanding by involvement, in the mode set up in the objectives for lesson delivery. Also, it is a movement in which the teachers, learners and resources are derived in the close range with one another for learning purpose. On the other hand, quality is defined as the

effort achievement of creating the most valuable outcomes on the market in most reasonable ways (Deming, 1982). Simply put, quality denotes an excellence in the delivery of instruction especially to the degree they conform to curriculum and satisfy students. In summing up these definitions quality extends to the promotion of collective knowledge of the educational procedures and institutional policies among educators, and being able to fulfill learners' desires and generate distinctive and proper features in the instructional procedure in order to bring out learning potential to attain the educational goals required by learners and their parents (Ko & Chung, 2014). The aforementioned proclamations therefore consent that education is largely depend on the instructor who is likely to be active in the discharge of their duties.

Consequently, quality learning is a concept termed with instruction (tutor) values which was examined by Afe (2003) as kind of teaching categorized by the exposition of logical, emotional and social stability, children admiration and love, and progressive personality towards achieving professional learning goals and capability to motivate noble potentials in learners. More so, quality teaching according to Henderson and Bibens (2009) is the capacity of teaching to inspire learners for various skills while integrating educational objectives and measuring the effective learning approach for the students. This is in line with the opinion of Evans (2006) who maintained that teaching quality measures the degree of realisation of instructional objectives. The author stress further that it is a clear progress in logical skills and capability as dignified by the achievements of learners. To this end, it is suffice to note that for teachers to deliver quality instruction in this 21st century in a way by which it enhances students' performance and awareness they have to be competent with. This is in line with the assertion of Asiyai (2013) who affirmed that providing education with no eminent value can even be more disastrous than no education at all, since without quality and valuable teaching, education has no worth.

Statement of the problem

Teaching for many years was used to be a noble career but it has been downplayed by impersonators who have no professional teaching

requirement in the school system. The inadequate teaching engagement opportunities predominant in Nigeria have enhanced flocking of the classrooms with non-qualified instructors who perceive teaching profession as a stepping-stone which would be abandoned the moment their choice of careers are gained. For example, a chemical engineering graduate who engages in the teaching of Mathematics, Chemistry or Physics in a senior school is considered as unprofessional teacher as such a teacher neither qualified to teach Physics because they did not study Mathematics, Physics Chemistry in Education nor having certificate in education. These teachers are not acquainted to the specifics of teaching; they lack knowledge of instructional methodology; they have low incentive and may not care much about their efficacy or quality of instruction given to student. It is in realisation of the present trends of employment of non-qualified teachers to impart in secondary schools in Kwara State, especially Ilorin Metropolis agitated the researcher to engage on the current research which is blended towards assessing the quality of teaching among secondary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions would guide this study:

1. What is the level of teaching quality among secondary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis?

2. What are the factors militating against quality teaching among secondary school teachers in Ilorin metropolis?
3. What are the suggested techniques for enhancing quality teaching among secondary school teachers in Ilorin metropolis?

Literature Review

Concept of Teaching

The conceptual definition of teaching has engendered a lot of controversy in the education field. While some scholar defined it as "the promotion of learning", others teaching as assisting other instructors to learn. According to the National Open University of Nigeria (2014), teaching is defined as understanding what the learners should know and methods of teaching the concepts in the most actual way of teaching. Teaching is also the significant skill that models the society in the best practices, the extent to which it is presented and its aggregate consequence on the societal lifespan (NOUN, 2014). John (2015) stressed further that instruction is an act by which a teacher directs the students in the attainment of learning, attitudes and skills. More so, it is a scheme of communication that involves the teacher, the learner and the learning resources, thus, making a wedge-shaped contact as revealed below:

At this point, it is crucial for the teacher to relate with students and the resources at the same time while students also can relate with both the resources and the teacher. Henderson and Bibens (2009) therefore emphasized that in the course of learning, there should be acceptable and mutual rapport between the teacher and the learners. This is vital since unwholesome affiliation may lead to learner's disaffection. Empirical evidence also

revealed that young learners love and acquire well with teachers who are friendly, helpful, kind, cheerful, patient, fair, possess sense of funniness, show of empathy for learner's difficulties, allow sufficient number of learners' activity and at the similar period preserve order (Evans, 2006). Therefore, the teacher should include all the learners in the school activities, position pertinent inquiries bearing in mind their class capabilities.

For this reason, the class activities should be learner-centred where learners would engage and discuss more than the educator whose role is to direct (NOUN, 2015). The author stated further that the instructor should also have a certain qualification for mastering over what the teacher teaches for effective manufacturing of sound learning. Such knowledge enhances self-concept and ensures that learners devote their time in a meaningful manner in school. Meanwhile, failure of the learners to do this may make them to look with contempt and disdain on the teacher. Such indifference may be communicated in form of derisive and walk-outs, or even denial to attend classroom activities.

Concept of Quality

The concept of value has fascinated various descriptions from numerous researchers. Webster's Seventh Collegiate Dictionary defined quality as atypical and vital personality of an essential feature; a degree of distinction; an extricate trait. Kalusi (2001) argued that quality is a multifarious idea and there is scarcely any compromise. Article 11 of the World Declaration on Education (2003) sees quality as a multi-various conception which should include all the meaningful programmes in schools. According to Ekong (2006) cited by Asiyai (2013), quality builds on understanding, perspectives, attitudes, live skills and values. Jaiyeoba and Atanda (2005) postulated that quality is tantamount to efficiency, standard, excellence, worthiness and relevance. Once application to education I made, it is the accomplishment with which a school delivers educational attainment which allows learners to achieve effectively in a valuable learning objectives with applicable academic standard (Ekundayo, 2010).

Teaching Quality

The term "teaching quality" and the tools for its assessment have created a lot of disagreement globally and therefore, there has been no acceptable definition of teaching quality since there is little or no common ground on what quality or good teaching entails. According to Remmers (2012) quality teaching is tantamount to learning where teacher effectiveness would be defined in three basic perspectives. These contain descriptions in terms of teachers' traits; interactions between teacher and learners; and their influence

on learner's comportment. Binakshi (2010) defined teaching quality as the competence and ability of a teacher to teach effectively. The author stressed further that teaching quality involves a set of teaching behaviours which are specifically effective in bringing about desired changes in students' learning. Barr (2012) explains the quality of teaching as a connection between pupils, teacher and the other people concentrates with the educational task. Johnson (2006) suggested three primary approaches to measuring quality teaching, namely;

- a) assessment of qualities supposed to function in the act;
- b) appraisal of teaching activity; and
- c) assessment of pupil intellectual/or academic growth.

An extended line of instructors' influence on learners' behaviour, Akpan (2006) signifying a practical view point, distinct instruction quality as the realisation of all or most of the knowledge purposes and discount of changes in intellectual stages among the students. This explanation is based on the knowledge that the preferred outcomes of teaching activities contain growth in intellectual skills, measured achievement gains, aptitude and improvement in attitude towards learning. Adepoju (2006) drives the discourse of quality teaching further in a conclusive manner. The author stated explicitly that good of preparation of lesson note, accurate use of scheme of work, effective use of instructional resources, observing learners' efforts and disciplinary capability are components of quality instruction which teachers' should maintain and defend effectively in the school system. It is in this direction, Onyekuru and Ibegbunam (2013) noted that quality of teaching would be unrushed through yearly report of teachers' activities in terms of performance in teaching, lesson preparation and lesson presentation, mastery of subject matter, competency, teachers' commitment to job and extra curricula activities.

Moreover, a survey carried out by Pachaiyappan and Ushalaya (2014) among developed secondary school lecturers in India revealed that school teachers' gender do not vary meaningfully in their teaching performance. Onyekuru and Ibegbunam (2013) equally carried out a study on teaching effectiveness in Rivers State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey study which

consists of 80 teachers in secondary school in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State was adopted. Findings of the research indicated that instructional efficiency of teachers from secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area was below average. The study also found that, teaching qualification and experience had a significant influence on teachers' effectiveness of the secondary school teachers, while gender had no significant influence in teaching and learning. In another related study, Okolocha and Onyeneke (2013) studied secondary school principals' perception of business studies teachers' teaching effectiveness in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study showed that teachers teaching Business Studies were unproductive in observing some features of classroom management, time management and lesson note preparation and class lesson delivery for optimum achievement of learning objectives and enhanced students' academic performance and subsequently employability.

The empirical studies examined showed that researches into teaching quality are mild but the little ones available were reviewed in relation to this study. To this end, personal observation by the researcher revealed that, most of these studies were on teaching effectiveness of teachers not teaching quality. Also, teaching quality variables like lesson planning/ instructional planning, subject matter proficiency, instructional strategies/ teaching methods, classroom organization and management and students' evaluation and outcome studied in this study make this study unique. For this reason, it is emphasized that this study ascertains the quality of learning among secondary school teachers in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria, to close the gap in knowledge and add to research knowledge in the field of teaching methodology.

Research Methodology

The descriptive survey method which necessitates a systematic collection of information from a population sampled through the use of an instrument was adopted for this study. This research type was chosen since the study intends to systematically and comprehensively collect information on the teaching quality variables of secondary school teachers' in Ilorin Metropolis.

The study area is Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria. The study was conducted in secondary schools within this area. The locale for

this study is the capital city of Kwara State in North-Central geo-political zone of Nigeria. It is divided into three Local Government Areas including Ilorin East, Ilorin South and Ilorin West. Records from the Ministry of Education and Human Capital Development (MEHCD), Kwara State, showed that Ilorin has 63 public senior secondary schools; 24 of these schools are in Ilorin South Local Government Area (LGA), 21 are in Ilorin West LGA, while 18 public secondary schools are in Ilorin East LGA.

The population of the study consists of all the 63 public senior secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis. Also, since the teachers' can best be evaluated by their superiors, the sample for this study constitutes 63 principals and 189 vice-principals in public secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis. Furthermore, by means of stratified random sampling method 36 out of the 63 public secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis were selected. The choice of this sampling technique was because it gave the researcher an opportunity of dividing the population into smaller subgroups called strata, prior to drawing the sample and then separate random samples are drawn from each of the strata. Also, the Principal and two (2) Vice-principals were selected from each of the thirty six (36) public secondary schools used for this study. This brought the total number of respondents used to 108.

The research instrument used in this study is a researcher's designed questionnaire titled "Teaching Quality Assessment Questionnaire" (TQAQ) which was divided into two sections- A and B. Section A consists of bio-data of the respondents. Section B consists of items that were used to determine the quality of teaching in areas of lesson planning/ instructional planning, subject matter proficiency, instructional strategies/ teaching methods, classroom organization and management and students' evaluation and outcome. The questionnaire is a closed ended form of questionnaire based on a four (4) point Likert scale, ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point.

TQAQ was subjected to both content and face validity by four experts in the fields of Curriculum Studies, Educational Technology and Measurement and Evaluation. In determining the reliability of the instrument, a trial-test on 20

respondents including the principal, 2 vice-principals and 17 teachers from secondary schools outside the area of the study was conducted. The outcome was calculated using Cronbach's coefficient based on their responses. The alpha values obtained was 0.89.

The researcher administered 108 copies of TEQ to the respondents to get or gather information with the use of direct delivery technique. The questionnaires were retrieved on the spot. In addition, data collected were analyzed using relevant descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation. The mean score statement were

interpreted as follows: 3.50 – 4.00 were categorised as high quality (HQ), 2.50 – 3.49, showed average quality (AQ), and mean values < 2.50 were classified as low quality (LQ). This interpretation also applies to the grand mean values.

Results, Analysis and Findings

This section deals with the presentation and analysis of data collected in the field for the study. The data analysis reflected the research objectives for the study. Therefore, the results were presented in tables according to the individual research questions.

Research Question 1: What is the level of teaching quality among secondary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the level of teaching quality of secondary school teachers' in Ilorin Metropolis

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	S.D	Dec.
LESSON PLANNING/ INSTRUCTIONAL PLANNING				
1	Teachers' lesson note contains clear and specific objectives of the lesson	3.16	0.84	AQ
2	Teachers' lesson note contains relevant and adequate information on the topic	3.45	0.76	AQ
3	Teachers' plan lesson in logical sequence	3.10	0.88	AQ
4	Teachers' use appropriate format of lesson note and use correct language in writing the lesson notes	3.06	0.90	AQ
	Overall Mean	3.19	0.85	AQ
SUBJECT MATTER PROFICIENCY				
5	Teachers' demonstrate command of the subject matter content	3.11	0.85	AQ
6	He/She demonstrates awareness of individual students learning needs	3.25	0.76	AQ
7	The teacher is versed in knowledge of his/her area of specialization	3.40	0.74	AQ
8	The teacher displays mastery and accuracy of subject content	3.57	0.68	HQ
	Overall Mean	3.33	0.76	AQ
INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES/ TEACHING METHODS				
9	The teacher use appropriate questioning techniques in the classroom	2.75	0.69	AQ
10	The teacher use ample and varieties of examples in teaching	2.25	1.01	LQ
11	The teacher is effective and efficient in the use of teaching aids	2.33	1.03	LQ
12	The teacher improvises unavailable instructional materials	1.71	0.94	LQ
	Overall Mean	2.26	1.03	LQ
CLASSROOM ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT				
13	Cordiality of teacher-pupils relation	2.22	0.98	LQ
14	Utilizes appropriate classroom rules and procedure	2.77	0.95	AQ
15	The teacher maintains a neat and orderly classroom environment conducive for learning	3.02	0.91	AQ
16	The teacher moves around the classroom to keep abreast of students' activities	1.75	1.04	LQ
	Overall Mean	2.44	0.97	LQ
STUDENTS' EVALUATION AND OUTCOME				
17	The teacher progressively measures students learning during lesson hour	3.36	0.88	AQ
18	The teacher measures students learning using multiple and varied levels of questions	2.27	1.02	LQ
19	Teachers' use assessment to solicit for information about students learning experiences	3.14	0.82	AQ
20	Teachers' show evidence of attainment of lesson objectives	3.06	0.90	AQ
	Overall Mean	2.95	0.91	AQ
	OVERALL GRAND MEAN	2.98	0.91	AQ

Key: S. D = Standard deviation, Dec. = decision, high quality (HQ), average quality (AQ) and low quality (LQ).

Regarding the level of teaching quality indicated in table 1, the overall mean values 3.19, 3.33, and 2.95 of the respondents' response revealed that the teaching quality of teachers in lesson planning/instructional planning, subject matter proficiency and students' evaluation and outcome were at average level. However, the overall mean values 2.26 and 2.44 of the respondents' response indicates that the teaching quality of teachers in areas of instructional strategies/ teaching methods and classroom organization and management were of low quality. Also, when summing up, the grand mean value of 2.95 revealed that the teaching quality among teachers in the sampled public secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis is above 2.50. This indicates that the teaching quality among secondary school teachers was at average level. This finding may be as a result of poor recruitment practices in which most of the teachers enter into the teaching profession. In fact, nowadays, it is popular for

persons who are burdened with the obligation of employing teachers into our public institutions to cater for specialized qualification for individual interest, favourism, political influence, ethnicity, etc. The results of this study was in agreement with the outcomes made in earlier researches (Okolocha and Onyeneke, 2013; Onyekuru and Ibegbunam, 2013) whose findings revealed moderate level of teachers effectiveness in secondary schools in Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What are the factors militating against quality teaching among in teachers in secondary school within Ilorin metropolis?

In analysing this research question, mean and standard deviation was used and a cut-off point of 2.50 was put into consideration. This means that if Mean > 2.5, the item is retained and when the Mean < 2.5, the item is rejected.

Table 2: Mean ratings of the respondents with regard to the factors militating against quality teaching among secondary school teachers in Ilorin metropolis

S/N	Questionnaire Item		S.D	Decision
21	Ineffective use of teaching aids	3.36	0.88	Accepted
22	Lack of creativity and innovativeness to improvise for unavailable instructional materials	3.95	0.72	Accepted
23	Low staff morale	3.64	0.73	Accepted
24	Ineffective teaching methods	3.53	0.56	Accepted
25	Use of outdated lesson notes	3.04	0.97	Accepted
26	Use of improper teaching techniques	3.48	0.63	Accepted
27	Poor construction of instructional objectives	3.25	0.76	Accepted
28	Poor instructional supervision	3.10	1.03	Accepted
29	Low remuneration and non -payment of teachers salaries	3.14	0.82	Accepted
30	Lack of vibrant staff development programmes	3.91	0.30	Accepted

Key: X = Mean, S. D = Standard deviation

Table 2 reveals the mean ratings of the opinions of the respondents with respect to the factors militating against quality teaching. The result from the table shows that the listed items 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29 and 30 had mean scores above 2.50 for acceptance. That is 3.36, 3.95, 3.64, 3.53, 3.04, 3.48, 3.25, 3.10, 3.14 and 3.91 respectively. This means that the respondents were in agreement that all the itemized factors militating against the quality of teaching among secondary school teachers in Ilorin metropolis,

Kwara State. However, the utmost essential features militating against the quality of teaching among teachers in secondary schools within Ilorin metropolis were lack of creativity and innovativeness to improvise for unavailable instructional materials, lack of vibrant staff development programmes, Low staff morale and ineffective teaching methods used by teachers with mean values 3.95, 3.91, 3.64 and 3.53 correspondingly.

Research Question 3: What are the suggested

strategies for enhancing quality teaching among teachers in secondary school within Ilorin metropolis?

In analysing research question 1, mean and standard deviation was used and a cut-off point of

2.50 was put into consideration. This implies that if Mean > 2.5, the item is retained and when the Mean < 2.5, the item is not accepted.

Table 3: Mean ratings of the respondents with Respect to the Techniques for enhancing quality teaching among secondary school teachers in Ilorin metropolis

S/N	Questionnaire Item		SD	Decision
31	Increased staff morale	2.96	0.96	Accepted
32	Effective use of instructional materials and improvement in the improvisation of instructional material/teaching aids	3.91	0.30	Accepted
33	Effective instructional supervision	3.50	0.88	Accepted
34	Use of active learning in class	2.63	0.78	Accepted
35	Use of cooperative learning	2.71	0.98	Accepted
36	Use of up to date material for teaching	3.25	0.76	Accepted
37	Improved condition of services for teachers like in the health sector	3.23	0.82	Accepted
38	Enhance teamwork between teachers	2.92	0.88	Accepted
39	Provision of functional library with up -to-date materials	3.31	0.81	Accepted
40	Provision of vibrant development programmes in relation to teaching methodology and pedagogy.	3.85	0.51	Accepted

Key: X = Mean, S. D = Standard deviation

Table 3 shows the mean ratings of the sampled teachers with respect to the techniques for enhancing quality teaching among secondary school teachers. From the table above, it can be seen that the responses of respondents on items 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39 and 40 were above the acceptance level of 2.50. This result shows that the responses support that all the listed items are effective strategies for enhancing quality teaching among secondary school teachers. However the most rated strategies for teaching quality were effective use of instructional materials and improvement in the improvisation of instructional material/teaching aids and provision of vibrant development programmes in relation to teaching methodology and pedagogy with mean values 3.91 and 3.85 respectively

Conclusion

On the outcomes from this work, the study has established that the teaching quality among teachers in secondary schools within Ilorin Metropolis was at average level. This average level of teaching quality may have a contrary view on the achievement of secondary education goals in terms

of poor students' academic achievement in both internal and external examinations in public secondary schools in Kwara State.

Recommendations

In line with the results and conclusion of this study, it is recommended among others that:

1. The government and school administrators should adopt the most rated strategies found in this study in order to enhance quality teaching among teachers in secondary school within the Ilorin metropolis and Kwara State in general.
2. Government should expose teachers to regular staff development programmes in teaching methodology in areas such as instructional strategies and effective classroom management in order to enhance their teaching quality. This can be done by organizing seminars, conferences and workshops to enable them keep abreast of the challenges posed by modern classroom challenges.
3. Lastly, teachers should endeavour to see classroom management as well as proper

use and improvisation of instructional materials as veritable tools for effective interaction, mastery and acquisition of requisite skills especially now that students' achievements at both internal and external examinations seem to be at its lowest ebb.

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